

***Anekântavâda* : Some observations**

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anekântavâda is the distinctive feature of the Jaina philosophy. Some scholars have tried to trace the doctrine in some of the speculations of the Vedic or the Buddhists systems. But we have shown in this study that the *anekântavâda* is chronologically underivable from the principles of any other system. It is thus, as Harisatyâ Bhattacharyya says, 'a unique doctrine of the Jaina philosophy and it is its original contribution to the course of the world thought'¹.

We may briefly examine the standpoint of *anekântavâda* and *syâdvâda* in the perspective of some Indian philosophical theories as follows:

With regard to the nature and status of ultimate reality the Vedânta proposes monistic theory; the Sâmkhya, dualistic theory; and the Bauddha and Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika are in favour of pluralistic theory from their own ontological standpoints. One may accept the Vedântic view that the substance or reality as the basis of all phenomena in ultimately one and eternal. But one cannot ignore the fundamental difference between the conscious and the unconscious in the phenomena, so he may also accepts that the substance or reality is not one, but two. Again if he closely looks at the phenomenal world he may realize the exclusive difference the souls, the material bodies, mind, time, space etc. as a result he may accepts that the reality or substance is neither one nor two, but many. The differences among the three views about the ultimate reality are thus the difference of ontological standpoints only. The different schools of philosophy oppose

each other only because as the Jainas points out that each of them regards its own ontological standpoint as the only possible standpoint and forgets that there may be other standpoints as well. So the Jaina philosopher does not hesitate to propose from the standpoint of their relativistic ontology and dialectical logic of *syâdvâda*: 1. The ultimate reality is one (*Vedânta*) in some respect; 2. It is dual (*Sâmkhya*) in some respect; 3. It is many-fold (*Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika*) in some respect. In the *Jaina anekântavâda-syâdvâda* 'the validity-to-some-extent', to which each of above schools can rightly lay claim, is acknowledged while their mutual oppositions are avoided. From such review it may be upheld that different philosophical systems taking their absolutist position may leap back from it and take a course essentially on the line of *anekântavâda-syâdvâda* in order to make their theories understandable.

'The Jainas hold' as S. N. dasgupta² opines, 'that the *Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika*, the *Vedânta*, the *Sâmkhya* and the Buddhists have each tried to interpret and systematize experience from one of the above points of view, and each regards the interpretations from his point of view as being absolutely true to the exclusion of all other points of view. This is their error (*nayâbhâsa*), for each standpoint represents only one of the many points of view from which a thing can be looked at. The affirmations from any point of view are thus true in a limited sense and under limited conditions. Infinite numbers of affirmations may be made of things from infinite points of view. Affirmations or judgments according to any *naya* or standpoint cannot therefore be absolute, for even contrary affirmations of the very self same things may be held to be true from other point of view. The truth of each affirmation is thus only conditional, and inconceivable from the absolute point of view. To guarantee correctness therefore each affirmation should be preceded by the phrase 'syât'.'

The Jaina philosophers, in a remote past, developed a new logic and ontology to solve the problem of the rivalry of all philosophical systems. 'In their *nayavâda*', says Sibajiban Bhattacharyya³, 'they presented their

solutions of the metaphysical problem by showing how different philosophical systems can all be seen to be valid from their own points of view. Recently K. C. Bhattacharyya developed the idea further to establish his theory of alternative forms of absolute — a theory which Kalidas Bhattacharyya called ‘*anekāntavedānta*’.

It is a matter of high appreciation that the logic of *anekānta* based *syādvāda* is so influential in the area of philosophical logic as according to some modern Indian scholars this logic can be translated in the language of modal logic and some other forms of modern western logic. In fact, being, non-being and indefinite or indescribable — the three categories of western logic are equally available in some sense or other in all the Jaina formulations of any and every kind of judgment following the theory of *syāt*. There is no universal and absolute position or negation, and all judgments are valid only conditionally. ‘The relation of the *naya* doctrine with the *syādvāda* doctrine’ S. N. Dasgupta⁴ says, ‘therefore this, that for any judgment according to any every *naya* there are as many alternatives as are indicated by *syādvāda*. The validity of such a judgment is therefore only conditional’.

That is why we find that B. K. Matilal’s approach to *syāt* statements involving the use of truth-functional propositional logic and the logic of quantification is strictly conditional. Although we have examined Matilal’s conditional interpretation of a *syāt*-predication in the *saptabhaṅgīnaya* and commented after the view of Gokhale that of interpretation were right, its consequences would be devastating for the Jaina philosophy as a whole.

Yet we cannot forget Matilal’s sincere attempts to convert the ancient logic of the Jaina into some form of modern symbolic logic of the west.

We have found that the *anekāntavāda* is still relevant in modern times and if we may make a sincere survey of the applications of this theory in various sphere of ones practical life. So it may rightly be said that the Jaina philosophy of *anekānta* has surpassed its theoretical boundary and reached our practical life to enlighten and enliven it with humanism. We

may see that each and every burning problem in the social, political, and religious domain either in a nation or in the world can be solved by the application of *anekāntavāda*. There is not a single field where *anekāntavāda* cannot be applicable. So, *anekāntavāda* is the best way of life. It is the supreme technique for management of quality of life.

Dr. Satkari Mookherjee says, ‘*anekānta* affirms the possibility of diverse attributes in a unitary entity. Strictly speaking, a thing is neither an absolute unity nor split up into an irreconcilable plurality. It is both unity and plurality of aspects’⁵. To add the words of Dayananda Bhargava to Dr. Mookherjee sayings: ‘this wider outlook of *anekānta* “avoids quarrels, which lead to marital conflicts and confrontations”⁶.

It is good to survey how Indian tradition, from *Ṛgveda* to Ramakrishna, have looked at this problem. The *Ṛgveda* has a well-known verse: ‘It is called *Indra*, *Mitra*, *Varuṇa* and *Agni*, and also *Garurātman*, the lovely-winged in heaven. The real is one, though known by different names (*ekamśadviprāvahudhāvadanti*)’⁷. The mystic saint Śrī Ramakrishna Paramahansa (1836-1886), who had tried successively Hindu, Muslim and Christian symbols as means of his *sādhanā*, and compared in a parable the various religions to the *ghāts* (banks or bathing places) around the same tank⁸. The Muslims take water from one *ghāt* and call it ‘*pāni*’, while the Hindus taking water from another *ghāt*, call it ‘*jal*’, and the Christians use a third *ghāt* and take what they call ‘water’. Though names are different, it is the same water. Swami Vivekananda spreads this doctrine of the equality of all religions and expected a universal religion all-over the world. Religions are like various rivers all leading to the sea. He said: ‘there never was my religion or yours, my national religion or your national religion; there never existed many religions, there is only the one. One infinite religion existed all through eternity and will ever exist, and this religion is expressing itself in various ways’⁹. like ‘so many rivers, having their source in different mountains, roll down, crooked or straight, and at last come to the ocean – so all these various creeds and religions, taking their start from different standpoints at last come unto thee’¹⁰. This

is the concept of tolerance embodied in Indian culture. Jaina doctrine of non-onesidedness (*anekānta*) provides a strong philosophical support to the concept of tolerance.

Ethical principles of tolerance in various forms found in the *Veda* and *Upanisads*, in the *Rāmāyaṇa* and *Mahābhārata*, in the *Bhagavad-Gītā*, in the *Dharmaśāstras*, in the philosophical literatures, in the teachings of Kabir, Guru Nanak, Sri Caitanya, Ramakrishna Paramahansa and others in the history of Indian culture. This unique trend is as old as the Vedas and undoubtedly forms an integral part of Indian culture from time immemorial. The famous Vedic saying we repeat, '*ekamsadviprābahudhāvadanti*' (one and the same reality is called by various names by the wise) provides the basis for universal tolerance and catholicity of outlook of Indian culture in general. And this attitude of 'tolerance', says N. Subrahmanian¹¹, stands for 'an attitude of mind and indicates a virtue bordering on graceful acceptance of the different and even the hostile; but in ordinary usage it also slightly smacks of supercilious condescension'. Viewing tolerance as the culture of peace, we may say that Jaina theory of *anekānta* is also a culture of peace, which contributes to the co-existence of diverse points of view and the tolerance of the value systems of others, and in this way it acts as the very root of the Indian tradition.

Tolerance, according to Jamal Khawaja¹², is a basic attitude towards others or as a moral value, usually develops under the following conditions: (a) awareness of plural truth-claims, (b) experience of existential perplexity, (c) spiritual autonomy or inner freedom, (d) awareness of distinction between subjective and objective truth, (e) awareness of man's cultural contingency, (f) respect for other minds or persons (g) capacity for empathy. We can, therefore, say without hesitation that the Jaina *anekāntavāda* is that very philosophical thought which truly represents the spirit of tolerance pervading the wide cultural outlook of Indian tradition and which appears to provide a strong philosophical support to the ideology of tolerance.

In fine following A. N. Upadhye we may say that the Jaina philosophers have taken the fullest advantage of *anekāntavāda* not only in building the system by a judicious search and balance of various viewpoints, but also in understanding sympathetically the views of others from which they differs and appreciating why there is difference between the two. This analytical approach to reality has saved the mankind from extremism, dogmatism and fanaticism and has further bred in him remarkable intellectual tolerance a rare virtue indeed¹³. *Anekānta* view is not skepticism, because it is not based on doubt and distrust, it is not solipsism, because it is based on an objective determination of things. It presents a catholic approach to the problems of life, T. G. Kalghatgi¹⁴ says. Following Ramakant Sinari¹⁵, we may say that, the Jaina theory of *anekānta* provides the culture of peace as a norm of conduct, an ideology at work. It can be the basis of the highest democratic and liberal values, viz., the coexistence of the diverse points of view, the habit of understanding and tolerance in one concerning the other paradigm and value scheme, the unconditional rejection of force in all inter-subjective, inter-communal and inter-national dealings, and the brotherhood among all without any injury by one to the dignity of the other. The humanistic message of Jainism thus may come to our life in the philosophical framework of a simple, easily understandable ever-living theory- *anekāntavāda*.

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